

Sample	PC1	PC2	PC3	Group
Young/Veh2	-2.5132976	-1.5817096	-0.1041644	Young/Veh
Young/Veh3	-3.2838104	0.54168364	0.15605205	Young/Veh
Young/Veh5	-2.10137	-0.6736259	0.57965663	Young/Veh
Young/Veh6	-1.900298	-1.0901688	-1.3593073	Young/Veh
Young/Veh7	-1.8271014	-0.7264461	-0.4543545	Young/Veh
Young/Veh8	-2.4991662	-1.1283356	-0.2422963	Young/Veh
Young/Veh9	-3.9723181	1.40774013	-1.7016861	Young/Veh
Young/Veh10	-0.9472649	-1.4965694	0.52343265	Young/Veh
Old/Veh1	1.33948573	1.58081997	0.83948673	Old/Veh
Old/Veh3	1.50849394	1.11379563	1.34616116	Old/Veh
Old/Veh4	5.00860559	-0.7909141	-0.8545194	Old/Veh
Old/Veh5	2.30679878	-1.251909	0.73255976	Old/Veh
Old/Veh6	4.56968967	-0.791908	-0.6655189	Old/Veh
Old/Veh7	1.85301179	1.78361771	0.98389129	Old/Veh
Old/Veh9	3.33013208	1.04276994	-0.3207095	Old/Veh
Old/PLX1	1.32841257	-1.1258459	-0.3709951	Old/PLX
Old/PLX2	-0.1570057	-0.7921566	1.09757931	Old/PLX
Old/PLX3	-0.7230529	0.65145164	1.04600134	Old/PLX
Old/PLX4	0.6047398	0.49634483	-2.1972247	Old/PLX
Old/PLX5	-1.1022628	1.9573181	-0.9161168	Old/PLX
Old/PLX6	-0.92225	-1.1219391	2.25816083	Old/PLX
Old/PLX7	1.79057891	-0.453645	-1.4269547	Old/PLX
Old/PLX8	-0.1988231	1.05796473	0.65966811	Old/PLX
Old/PLX9	-1.4919279	1.39166691	0.39119796	Old/PLX

Step.Cycle

Stand

Body.Speed

Swing

Social.Interaction

Tail.Suspension

Regularity.Index

NORT

Stride.Length

Forced.Swim

NORT

Stride.Length

Social.Interaction

Tail.Suspension

Regularity.Index

Body.Speed

Stand

Step.Cycle

Forced.Swim

Swing

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